

Correlation between Teacher-Made-Test and Senior School Certificate Examination Geography Scores among students in Dass Educational Zone, Bauchi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Quality teaching had reflected on students' learning outcomes and academic performances in senior secondary school (SSS) Geography. The internally conducted assessments in schools were used as mock evaluations in the preparation for success in the SSS certificate examination. Based on this, research was developed to investigate if there were correlations between students' scores in mock (TMT) SSCE and their scores in WASSCE and NECO for geography. The study adopted the Ex-post facto research design, total population of six hundred and forty (640) students' while the sample for this study consisted of senior secondary school students that sat for 2021 and 2022 WASSCE, and NECO. The results were obtained and analysed while Pearson's product moment correlation (PPMC) and descriptive statistics were used for analyses and to answer research questions and hypotheses. The findings revealed that there is no correlation between the school-based assessment and WAEC 2021, 2022 Geography certificate examinations. Thus, study recommended that geography teachers should be more active in implementing curriculum as appropriated, particularly in matters relating to preparations for external examinations, so as to foster overall positive academic performances in TMT and external examinations.

Keyword: Teacher Made Test, External examinations, Geography

Introduction

In recent times, there were concerns on the academic performance of senior secondary school students' compare with internal scores (teacher made test score). Teacher Made Test has being important and significant for student developments in teaching-learning activities. In Nigeria, educational planners, evaluators and administrators are now more conscious than ever before of their role in the nationwide scheme of curriculum innovation (Mkpae and Obowu 2017; Martins, 2024). Research had been done in area of value-based pedagogy and integrating diversity in education which lead the research identified and integrated four essential dimensions—Universal Values, Understanding, Respect for Differences, and Inclusivity—into a cohesive pedagogical framework, providing a culturally responsive and adaptable structure that addresses the unique challenges of values education in a diverse society (Nik Muhammad Hanis et. al., 2025; Abass, 2015). In other word, a well monitored curriculum by the administrators and teachers planned activities should be based on curriculum inclusive while students are readily available for learning. It should be considered that not only have new courses been introduced and new contents injected into existing subjects without teachers planned activities through value based curriculum (Martins, 2024). This may course a fundamental change in the system of assessment of students' performance and may has effects on formalization of Teacher Made Test as a major component of evaluation process.

Therefore, Teacher Made Test had been an effective classroom assessment which required skills and practices as students react to achieve their immediate objectives. It is the basic need of the teacher to improve the standard of learning because they have greater responsibility to design quality assessment that aligns with the students learning outcome (OECD 2015). Teachers have opportunity to continuously monitor their students and give constructive feedback to improve students' learning abilities. School-based assessment in terms of validity and flexibility was acknowledged and at the same time examination bodies have to grow against or deal with difficulties related to reliability, while immense potential of quality control and quality assurance. It is important to point out that although conceptually distinct, both external and school-based assessments have their strengths and weaknesses. External assessment is reliable and is perceived as rigorous because candidates take the same assessment administered under similar conditions. School-Based assessment, if carefully planned and implemented may be stronger in terms of validity and flexibility. Grina (2015) differentiated between the two by stating that

in external assessment, the awarding body is in direct control of the mark or grade awarded to each candidate through the individuals it appoints to make the assessment decisions, as against school-based assessment where the final decision is made by the teachers and the respective schools.

The problems of examination imbalance in Nigeria have made it practically difficult to correlate student's actual performance in National examinations or certificate examinations with teacher made test scores in order to be sure that internally assessment scores is a lead way for high score made by the student through external examinations performance. Besides, the internally conducted assessments in schools were used as mock evaluations in the preparation for success in the SSS certificate examination. This prompted the present study investigate the correlation between teacher made test and senior secondary school Geography certification examination in Dass Educational Zone, Bauchi state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

1. To find out the relationship between Geography of Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Students' WAEC2021/2022 in Geography
2. To examine the relationship between Geography of Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Students' NECO2021/2022 in Geography

Teacher Made Test has been included as part of the requirement for any certificate examination in Nigeria. It was introduced to compliment the scores of prospective students for the award of certificates. It is a term which emerged from a change in the conception of assessment as a tool for only identifying students for further education, training and employment, to one geared towards enhancing knowledge. It involves a combination of centralized and teacher made test. This change of interest is consequent on education not yielding the desired results; products of schools were certified but lacked the where with all enhancement of learning for the individual. The introduction of teacher made test should engender a positive attitude and not a laissez-faire behavior. Teacher Made Test was given great impetus by the National Policy on Education (2014) when it was indicated that it will constitute a part of all examinations.

Internal examination includes all tests that are conducted from time to time in schools. These tests were conducted firmly at the end of the school year and were used continually for the promotion of students from one class to another or from one level to another. Also, the internal system of assessment is to prepare the student for external examination purposes. External examinations on the other hand are those conducted by external bodies and agencies that had no hand in teaching the students. These bodies include the Ministry of Education, West African Examination Council (WAEC), and National Examination Council (NECO). The old system was found to be full of weakness because it concentrated on one aspect of human development which is cognitive domains. Furthermore, the interest of Teacher Made Test is a shift from teaching for examination to teaching for acquisition of knowledge and understanding. It is expected to expand the form, the mode and the scope of the assessment in schools to facilitate and enhance learning. The implementation calls for the utilization of assignments, projects, practical work, group work, and the conventional assessment techniques, otherwise called authentic techniques.

There is good number of characteristics which distinguishes Teacher Made Test from other forms of assessment. For instance, school-based assessment requires teachers to plan assessment programme, identify appropriate assessment tests for students and be involved in making judgments. Teacher Made Test allows for the collection of samples of student's performance over a period of time. It can also be adopted and modified to match the teaching and learning of a particular class and the students assessed (OECD 2015). It has been argued that testing only motivates teachers and students to work towards performance goals rather than learning goals. Greater value has been placed on testing since the inception of formal education based on the fact that tests are the basic reporting mechanism for the yearly progress of the children. Before the introduction of teacher made test, the testing of students through a single examination administered at the end of the year had been regular practice throughout our educational system (OECD 2015).

Similarly, Teacher Made Test, significant changes in teachers' perception of teaching and the role they play have been identified. Teachers have started to see teaching as a facilitator of student's learning rather than merely completing the curriculum. In other development, the perception of teachers on students as having a fixed level of ability have also started to change as they begin to observe that their students are able to own up their works and are free to take more responsibility for their learning and become more independent learners and enjoy the freedom they have in the assessment process. When students become more independent learners, skills are developed in extreme recognition with reliable confidence in learning outcomes. It is possible, for instance, to identify candidates who scored 'A1' in the NECO SSCE and has poor cumulative scores in the teacher made test of the same subject and in the same year therefore, external assessment also important.

Assessment of data can be obtained from directly examining students' work to assess the achievement of learning outcomes or can be based on other data from which one can make inferences about learning. As a continuous process, assessment establishes measurable and clear students' learning outcomes, providing a sufficient amount of learning opportunities to achieve these outcomes, implementing a systematic way of gathering, analyzing and interpreting evidence to determine how well students learning matches expectations and using the collected information to inform improvement on students' learning. The term assessment is generally used to refer to all the activities teachers use to help students learn and guard their progress. Adeleke (2015), assessment is a powerful diagnostic tool that enables learners to understand their areas of strengths and weaknesses either by School-Based or certification examinations. Similarly, Odinko (2014) views assessment as the process of observing, recording and documenting what learners do and how they do it as a basis for a variety of educational decisions that affect the learner. It connotes a process of organizing measurement data into interpretable forms to aid decision making. According to UNESCO (2020), teacher made test is defined as students' assessments that are regularly organized and administered by each educational institution established in a country. Assessment tools are generally designed by the teachers. The results are used to provide direct feedback to students and parents, to regulate the classroom and improve the teaching-learning process. In some countries, scores to these assessment counts (weight on the final score) for the graduation or selection of students. Teacher made test is essential in our education system as it is part of our national strategy to improve the quality of education. It is a transformation system as it scales down the emphasis on examination-orientated teaching and teaches (Siti et al, 2019).

Basically, teacher made test requires teachers to monitor students' learning progress, evaluating students' performance, recording students' progress and providing feedback from time to time. Teacher Made Test is a type of assessment that incorporates different categories of people (teacher, parents and peers) into the process of determining learning outcomes in other to support and motivate a child to become interested in learning and make regular and consistent academic progress. Students spend the best part of their young lives in school and it is through the teachers' assessment that abilities can be better understood. Beyond the above characteristics of Teacher Made Test, it is also comprehensive, systematic, continuous, diagnostic and integrative as directed by the teacher. This assessment procedure originates from the classroom situation requiring active participation and involvement of students with an emphasis on learning rather than the importance of scores and grades. Test Made Test involves the continuous assessment of students at intervals in the three domains of learning vis-à-vis cognitive, affective and psychomotor using different instruments such as test, assignment, observation, interview, questionnaire and project.

The second category of assessment is called certificate examinations. This form of assessment is carried out to award a certificate to indicate the mastery level of the examinee. It is known as external examination which is organized by experts outside an examinee's school, college or university. Certificate examination is that type of assessment organized and administered by examination bodies outside the school. Individual schools have no control over it because it is external and it produces a summative evaluation of candidates (Tarum, 2016). The academic school-learning qualification awarded upon successful completion of the examinations is the West African Senior School Certificate which is the academic qualification awarded upon successful completion of the examination is Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). Teacher Made Test and Certificate Examination While examination bodies acknowledge the immense potential of teacher made test in terms of validity and flexibility, at the same time they have to grow against or deal with difficulties related to reliability, quality control and quality assurance. It is important to point out that although conceptually distinct, both external and teacher made test have their strengths and weaknesses.

It is therefore, on this basis that several scholars in the field of educational assessment advocate the need for a combination of both forms of assessment. Grina (2012) also confirmed that it has become a widely held opinion that a mix of external and internal assessment provides a comprehensive approach to the assessment of educational achievement. Educational assessment procedures remain the corner-stone for establishing the quality, relevance and effectiveness of the instructional processes in the schools. This is informed by the whole lot of attention and resources committed to this aspect of the educational system (Aminu, 2012). There is the belief that without realistic educational assessment in schools it will be very difficult to obtain necessary information as feedback from classroom instruction. This is needed for objective decision on the academic tone of the teacher made test on the performance of the learners.

Geography is a subject in secondary schools which deal with nature and natural resources for human consumption. In order to determine the if there is relationship between the internal and external examination towards student academic performance, as the students, parents, educational stakeholders blame teachers for such discrepancies in student's academic performance in regard to teacher made test and certificate examinations. As a teacher (researcher), it is very important for students academic performance in teacher made test to correlate with that of the certificate examinations been administered to

the learners in school setting but if revise is the case then there must be a reasons for such discrepancies that is the reasons that trigger this study. Therefore, there is a need to carry out correlation of Geography Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Geography in Dass Educational zone of Bauchi State, Nigeria. Thus, the following research question and hypothesis guided the study:

Research Questions

1. Is there any relationship between Geography of Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Students' WAEC2021/2022 in Geography?
2. Is there any relationship between Geography of Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Students' NECO2021/2022 in Geography?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and to be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- i. **H₀₁**: there is no significant relationship between Geography of Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Students' WAEC 2021/2022 in Geography
- ii. **H₀₂**: there is no significant relationship between Geography of Teacher Made Test Scores and Performance of Senior Secondary School Students' NECO 2021/2022 in Geography

Methodology

Internally conducted assessments in schools are supposed to be used to ascertain students who are likely to succeed in the final externally conducted examination. What therefore remains disturbing is whether a relationship exists between Teacher Made Test scores and SSCE examination results in secondary schools most especially the study carrying out in Dass Education State, Nigeria. The present study adopted Ex-post facto research design with total sample of six hundred and forty (640) students' while the sampled surveyed for this study consisted of senior secondary school students who sat for 2021 and 2022 WASSCE, NECO.

In order to simplify the result findings, a formulated WAEC and NECO Senior School Certificate Examinations Results Form (WNSSCE-RF) was used as manual to obtaining the secondary school students results information from schools, while the results obtained were subjected to Pearson's Product Moment Correlation for correlation analysis in order to answer the research questions and test the hypothesis of the study.

Results

Research Question 1: "Is there any relationship between Teacher Made Test Score 2021 (TMT) and Performance of Senior Secondary School Geography Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography?" For the total students' geography grades, table1 indicates the summary of TMT 2021 geography grades' results of samples involved in the research from 20 schools in Dass Educational Zone of Bauchi State. The below descriptive statistics of Teacher Made Test Scores (TMT) 2021 students' Geography Grades: Using the table below, Grades/sample in number 1 means that 8 students had A1, B3 only 3 students and so on. At the end total, 79 students had A1, 53 students had B2, 42 students had B3, 51 students had C4, 33 students had C5, 30 students had C6, 5 students had D7, 21 students had E8 and 1 student had F9. The researcher collected the secondary data as a raw score and converted into grading system.

Table1: Showing Descriptive Statistics (TMT) 2021 Students' Geography Grades

Grades/ Samples	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	No. Of Schools
1	8	3	1	5	1	2	0	0	0	20
2	4	4	2	6	3	0	0	1	0	20
3	3	6	3	2	4	1	0	1	0	20
4	4	5	2	4	2	2	0	1	0	20
5	4	4	4	1	3	2	1	1	0	20
6	3	4	2	4	1	1	2	3	0	20
7	5	4	7	1	1	2	0	0	0	20
8	6	3	4	1	2	2	1	1	0	20
9	7	3	3	5	0	1	0	1	0	20
10	6	3	2	3	4	0	0	2	0	20
11	7	2	1	3	3	3	0	1	0	20
12	3	4	3	3	1	3	0	3	0	20
13	4	3	1	4	2	5	0	1	0	20
14	3	4	2	5	0	4	1	1	0	20
15	8	2	1	2	3	1	0	3	0	20
16	4	2	6	2	3	1	0	1	1	20
Total	79	53	42	51	33	30	5	21	1	320

The table above, shows the summary of teacher made test scores 2021 students offered Geography which the researcher used to describe the relationship between the variables. From the table above, sixteen (16) SS3 students were sampled from twenty (20) schools making the total of three hundred and twenty students (320). The researcher collected the data in raw and converted into grading system as shown in the above table1.

Table2 Showing the summarized WAEC 2021 geography grades' results of samples involved in the research from 20 schools of Dass Educational Zone of Bauchi State for further analysis.

Grades/ Samples	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	No. Of Schools
1	0	2	4	4	4	5	0	1	0	20
2	0	1	3	3	5	7	1	0	0	20
3	0	2	2	2	8	6	0	0	0	20
4	0	2	3	5	3	6	1	0	0	20
5	0	1	3	7	4	4	1	0	0	20
6	1	2	3	2	4	7	0	1	0	20
7	0	1	5	4	2	6	2	0	0	20
8	1	1	3	4	3	5	1	2	0	20
9	0	3	4	2	8	1	1	0	1	20
10	0	4	2	3	4	5	2	0	0	20
11	1	2	3	5	1	7	1	0	0	20
12	0	2	3	6	2	5	2	0	0	20
13	0	0	3	3	6	4	3	1	0	20
14	0	2	3	1	6	5	2	1	0	20
15	0	2	1	5	3	4	3	0	2	20
16	1	1	4	4	5	2	1	2	0	20
Total	4	28	49	60	68	79	21	8	3	

Table2 Shows the summary of WAEC 2021 students offered Geography which the researcher used to describe the relationship between the variables. From the table above, sixteen (16) SS3 students were sampled from twenty (20) schools making the total of three hundred and twenty students (320). In order to simplify the grades, table3 shown the cumulative grades for easier description between TMT 2021 and WAEC 2021 Geography results. Table 3: Showing the students grades of SBA and WAEC 2021 Geography results as follows:

Table3 Showing the summary of Teacher Made Test 2021 and WAEC 2021 Geography

Exams	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	N
TMT 2021	79	53	42	51	33	30	5	21	1	20
WAEC 2021	4	28	49	60	68	79	21	8	3	20

However, the highest grade achievement of student in Teacher Made Test 2021 was 79 students with A1 while the highest grade achievement of student in WAEC of 2021 Geography was C6 by 79 students. It can be compared that student have high grade in teacher made test 2021 than WAEC 2021 Geography in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. By implication, students' academic achievement in Teacher Made Test is good but it does not relate with the students' academic achievement in WAEC which it could be as a result of other factors. Thus, Table 4 was constructed to test the hypothesis either rejected or accepted of null hypothesis.

Test of the hypothesis

H₀₁ there is no significant relationship between Teacher Made Test Scores 2021 and Performance of Senior Secondary School Geography Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC). Correlation is often used to explore the relationship between variables. The results of the above question regarding any relationship between School-Based Assessment 2021 (SCAS/SBA) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography results based on t-test analysis as shown in the table 4 below.

Table4: Showing the relationship between Teacher Made Test 2021 and WAEC 2021 Geography

Exams	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	N	R	Sig	H ₀₁
TMT 2021	79	53	42	51	33	30	5	21	1	20	.081	.735	Accepted
WAEC 2021	4	28	49	60	68	79	21	8	3	20			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the above table, relationship between Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography results was too low. There was a weak correlation between the two variables $r=.081$, $n=320$, $p<.01$ with high levels of Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) and low level of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography results. Hypothesis was accepted that there is no relationship between Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography as illustrated in table 4. The findings revealed that School-Based Assessment 2021 (SCAS/SBA) not lead to increase of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography results among students in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State.

The Research Question 2

Is there any relationship between Teacher Made Test (TMT) 2021 and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (NECO) 2021 Geography?" For the total students' geography grades, table 4.1 indicates the summary of teacher made test 2021 geography grades' results of samples involved in the research from 20 schools in Dass Educational Zone of Bauchi State.

Table4: Shows the summary of teacher made test 2021 Geography grades. The scores was collected as a raw and converted by the researcher to grading system as follows:

Grades/ Samples	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	No. Of Schools
1	8	3	1	5	1	2	0	0	0	20
2	4	4	2	6	3	0	0	1	0	20
3	3	6	3	2	4	1	0	1	0	20
4	4	5	2	4	2	2	0	1	0	20
5	4	4	4	1	3	2	1	1	0	20
6	3	4	2	4	1	1	2	3	0	20
7	5	4	7	1	1	2	0	0	0	20
8	6	3	4	1	2	2	1	1	0	20
9	7	3	3	5	0	1	0	1	0	20
10	6	3	2	3	4	0	0	2	0	20
11	7	2	1	3	3	3	0	1	0	20
12	3	4	3	3	1	3	0	3	0	20
13	4	3	1	4	2	5	0	1	0	20
14	3	4	2	5	0	4	1	1	0	20
15	8	2	1	2	3	1	0	3	0	20
16	4	2	6	2	3	1	0	1	1	20
Total	79	53	42	51	33	30	5	21	1	

Table4: Showing summary of Teacher Made Test 2021 Students School Geography Scores

The table above shows the summary of the school-based assessment year 2021 Geography of three hundred and twenty students who offered geography.

The summarized NECO 2021 geography grades' results of samples involved in the research from 20 schools of Dass Educational Zone of Bauchi State for further analysis as follows:

Table5: Showing the summary of NECO 2021 Geography Students' Achievement Grades

Grades/ Samples	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	No. of Schools
1	0	4	2	2	4	2	4	2	0	20
2	0	0	3	9	3	2	2	1	0	20
3	1	2	3	3	3	5	2	1	0	20
4	0	2	1	4	4	6	2	1	0	20
5	1	1	3	3	6	5	0	0	1	20
6	1	1	1	6	4	6	1	0	0	20
7	0	1	1	9	7	2	0	0	0	20
8	0	1	2	3	2	5	3	3	1	20
9	0	1	2	5	6	2	2	1	1	20
10	0	0	3	8	2	5	1	1	0	20
11	1	2	1	6	5	3	2	0	0	20
12	1	2	1	2	5	7	2	0	0	20
13	1	1	3	3	5	6	0	0	1	20
14	1	3	2	2	5	7	0	0	0	20
15	2	1	2	5	4	4	2	0	0	20
16	0	2	4	5	4	3	1	1	0	20
Total	9	24	34	75	69	70	24	11	3	

The above table5: shows the summary of NECO 2021 Geography grades of three hundred and twenty students which the researcher used to describe the relationship between the two variables.

Table 6: Showing the Descriptive statistics of Teacher Made Test 2021 and NECO 2021 Geography

Exams	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	N
TMT 2021	79	53	42	51	33	30	5	21	1	20
NECO 2021	9	24	34	75	69	70	24	11	3	20

The above table was used to describe the relationship between Teacher Made Test and NECO 2021 Goegraphy Students' academic Achievement. However, the highest grade achievement of student in teacher made test 2021 was 79 students with A1 while the highest grade achievement of student in NECO of 2021 Geography was C4 by 75students. It can be compared that student have high grade in teacher made test 2021 than NECO 2021 Geography in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. Thus, Table 6 was constructed to test the hypothesis either rejected or accepted of null hypothesis.

Test of hypothesis:

HO₂: there is no significant relationship between teacher made test 2021 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography. Correlation is often used to explore the relationship between variables. The results of the above question regarding any relationship between Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography results based on Pearson's correlation analysis as shown in the table 7 below:

Table7: Showing the Relationship between Teacher Made Test 2021 and NECO 2021 Geography

Exams	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	N	R	sig	H0
TMT 2021	79	53	42	51	33	30	5	21	1	20	.083	.728	Accepted
NECO 2021	9	24	34	75	69	70	24	11	3	20			

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows relationship between the variables under study that's the relationship between Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography results was low. There was a weak correlation between the two variables $r=.083$, $n=320$, $p<.01$ with high levels of teacher made test 2021 (TMT) and level of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography results. Hypothesis was accepted that there is no relationship between School-Based Assessment 2021 (SCAS/SBA) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography as illustrated in table 7. The findings revealed that Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) not lead to increase of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography results among students in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from this research indicates acceptance of hypothesis that there is no relationship between teachers made test 2021 and 2022 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 and 2021 (WAEC) Geography in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. This indicated that teacher made test 2021 and 2022 (TMT) not increase the student ability of getting high scores in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 and 2022 (WAEC) Geography in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that Teacher Made Test scores in Geography did not individually significantly improve/relate student's grades in WAEC 2021, 2022 Geography. The finding of this present study contradicts the position of Adekeye (2011) that teacher made test scores has positive relationship in BECE JSS3 performance followed by JSS1 and JSS2 in English language. This obvious contradiction could be attributed to the fact that the reviewed study focused on Junior Secondary School while current study focused on senior secondary school. The contradiction could further be accounted for by the students and the teachers in the area of the study.

Meanwhile, the finding from this research indicates rejection of hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Teacher Made Test in 2021 and 2022 (TMT) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 and 2022 (NECO) Geography in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. This indicated that teacher made test 2021 and 2022 (TMT) not increase the student ability of getting high scores in Senior Secondary School Geography Certificate Examinations 2021. This trend could be traceable to the fact that the Geography teachers fell short of using the school-based assessment to prepare the students for SSCE Geography. It could further be traced to the fact that the Teacher Made Test was not subjected to rigorous item analysis. This finding is in disagreement with the averment of Opara, Onyekuru and Njoku (2015) that the combination of the teacher made test scores significantly predicted students' English achievement in JSCE. The aforementioned inconsistency may not be separated from factors such as variation in sample attributes scope and area coverage of the study.

Meanwhile, only in 2022 (NECO) Geography result slightly increased in term of correlation in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. The slightly change in relationship position indicate more commitment by the teachers toward student improvement in geography. This finding was consistence with the study by Frazer and Beuke (2011) who maintained that, there is always a positive relationship between the teacher made test scores and final High School Examination Results. In the same vein, this finding agrees with Edwin (2014) and Mwebaza (2016) who rightly observed that, high regression exist between teacher made test scores and final examinations such as WAEC and NECO. The findings revealed that there was insignificant relationship between the NECO and WAEC Geography of both 2021 and 2022 results. This implies that students perform better in WAEC 2021 and 2022 Geography results than NECO 2021 and 2022 Geography results. This finding is in inline with Grace et. al. (2023) revealed that students 'SSI, SSII and SSIII English Language scores did not significantly jointly predict their grades in SSCE English Language. There was insignificant relationship between the teacher made test in 2021, 2022 and Geography certificate examinations WAEC 2021, 2022 respectively. Students tend to perform better in school assessment than WAEC certificate examination.

Conclusion

Although, internally conducted assessments in schools were used as mock evaluations in the preparation for success in the SSS certificate examination but the findings from this present study revealed that School-Based Assessment 2021 (SCAS/SBA) not lead to increase of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (WAEC) Geography results among students in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. Based on this, research was further investigated if there were correlations between students' scores in mock (TMT) SSCE and their scores in WASSCE and NECO for geography. The findings revealed that Teacher Made Test 2021 (TMT) not lead to increase of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations 2021 (NECO) Geography results among students in Dass educational zone of Bauchi State. This is consistent with recent research of Nik Muhammad Hanis et. al., (2025) which emphasized that correlate the curriculum and integrate the value can enhance values education by addressing the complexities of diverse classrooms, helping educators create culturally responsive and inclusive learning experiences.

Recommendations

The federal and state ministry of education should put in place regular checks and balances to ensure that teacher made test follows good procedure in all secondary school. A uniform policy on the practice should be emphasized and reemphasized so that all the schools will benefit from it. Similarly, study recommended that all Geography teachers are advised to dig more into trending issues and follow the current syllabus to ensure conformity between teachers made test and external examination.

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